

THE PLACE OF PRECEDENT NAMES IN UZBEKI AND ENGLISH ARTISTIC TEXTS

Davletova Shoxida

Graduate student of Urganch State University,

Department of Linguistics (English)

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Abstract: The role of precedent names in the Uzbek and English literary texts are analyzed in this article.

Key words: onomastic units, language poetics, language culturology, antraponomial, toponyms, zoonyms, analytical method.

As we all know, there are various means of creating an artistic text, which bring the text to life in all its aspects. It should be said that the means of forming the artistic text are considered different, and among them precedent units have a special place. What is a predicate unit?

Precedent unit is a tool that exists in the linguistic memory of these people as a language unit, and is repeatedly referred to in the formation of an artistic text. To determine the precedent units, it is necessary to work with the context, the meaning obtained from it serves to clarify the precedent units. One type of precedent unit is precedent nouns. Precedent units are one of the main objects of study of linguo-cultural studies, which is one of the leading directions of language system research. Personal names, stable phrases, sentences, and texts that are well known to the speakers of a certain language and are stored in their linguistic memory, are repeatedly referred to in their speech activity, are recorded as precedent units. In his research on intertextuality, N. Pego-Gro divides precedent units into four:

1. *Quote;*
2. *Reference;*
3. *Extract without quotes;*
4. *Allusion.*

Precedence is related to the concept of intertextuality, or rather, it is a phenomenon included in it. Precedence is one of the manifestations of intertextuality, and it is characterized by the fact that it is well known to the main layer of language speakers and is used repeatedly in speech. Among precedent units, precedent names have a special place. According to V.A. Maslova, personal names associated with well-known texts or events can be precedent names. A writer can create a text using only one precedent name tool. For example: Ali Baba is the name of the hero of the tale "One Thousand and One Nights". The name of the hero of the fairy tale repeated in the poem does not require any further explanation as it is a precedent name. It is easily understood by the reader. This anthroponym served to form the intonation structure of the poem. At the same time, he created multi-layeredness based on intertextuality. *Ali Baba*, There are still people in this world, Bob. Let the human bird look for the good ones, get used to the bad ones and sometimes make mistakes, make mistakes! (*A. Abidjan. Grandfather Ali*).

Precedent nsoms are different according to the motive of appearance. They can be related to artistic texts, religious texts, famous and interesting events, legends, narratives, fairy tales,

anecdotes, songs, and movies. For example, names such as *Layli*, *Majnun*, *Shum bola*, *Sotti*, *Nasriddin Efandi*, *Khizr*, *Karabotir*, *Tahir-Zuhra* are popular among Uzbeks. Precedent names can be connected with the national mentality of representatives of a certain nation, but also of a global nature. For example, an Uzbek student can easily understand the content of texts with names such as Napoleon, Columbus, Buratino, Charlie Chaplin, Othello, Don Juan, Robinson Crusoe, Jackie Chan, and Mr. Bean. An important psycholinguistic feature of precedent names in a literary text is that they require the actualization of non-textual meaning in the mind of the reader of the text, that is, additional information related to the text, but not included in its verbal structure. It is important for the reader to know the importance of non-textual meaning in the pragmatic structure of the text. For example: Gulliver is the hero of Jonathan Swift's *Gulliver's Travels*. A dwarf man. In the poem, the lyrical hero writes that he fell into the land of dwarfs in a dream. It has a figurative meaning. That is, under the pretext of saying that it is difficult to live among small people, small-talking people are condemned. That's the point - I was Gulliver in my dream and fell into the pits, but I didn't go away because of them, I died and woke up, my husband... (*B.Isu. I was Gulliver in my dream...*)

We will cover the precedent names in more detail with examples. *JAYHUN* is one of the ancient names of Amudarya. The Jayhun hydronym was used in poetic texts instead of the name Amudarya and was a tool for creating a high poetic style. Also, the archaic hydronym of Jayhun creates in the reader's mind the association that Amudarya is an ancient river. This is how Jayhun is beating down below, and night is falling on the bosom of Sahara. (A. Oripov. August). You waved like a river of Jayhun... You are a jewel in my heart, Motherland. (*M. Ollomurodov. Motherland*). The flowers opened like the expression of longing, the winds of Esar Jayhun like the performance of flower girls. (S. Sayyid. Esar Jayhun winds). We will also give examples of precedent names from world literature. *COLUMBUS* Christopher Columbus (1451-1506) was a Spanish explorer who discovered America for Europeans in 1492. Referring to this meaning through the name of Columbus caused the emergence of metaphorical imagery in the artistic text.

Sharia! This belief is unrelentingly repeated, dragging me towards mysterious discoveries. The flag of my loyalty to you is that, every time, in every poem, every time I kick my heart, if I am in my own heart, Columbia. (O. Matjon. Poetry). And suddenly you notice: not people, but ships are sailing across the street - they are going to open America, not to the office, not to the pub. You want to shout and congratulate them, And suddenly you realize: You are also a Columbus. (U.Azim. Kolumb). The cited examples show that the precedent phenomena existing in the linguistic consciousness of Uzbek and world language speakers have created a unique microsystem in the language system.

As a conclusion, we can say that precedent names, which are considered a certain type of precedent units, are used in the text, together with references to historical and famous persons, they contribute to the more impressive and meaningful output of the text. Whether they are concrete or abstract depends on the discretion of the author, and it is appropriate for poets to comment on unknown precedent names.

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